

PEER EFFECT OF CORPORATE FINANCIALIZATION: BASED ON INTERLOCKING DIRECTOR NET- WORKS

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

In recent years, the trend of corporate financialization has become increasingly evident, with many non-financial corporations investing large amounts of capital in high-yield, fast-returning areas such as financial markets and real estate. According to the CSMAR database, the share of companies holding financial assets among non-financial listed companies in China was well over 80% during 2006-2020 and reached a stage peak of 91.2% in 2017. In addition, the level of financialization of companies is steady at 5%-7%, and the ratio of profits from financial channels to EBITDA basically remains at 14%-17%. That is, financial assets have become an essential asset component for the entity, while profitability from financial assets has become an important complementary channel for its profits. Previous studies have revealed the motivations (Baud & Durand, 2012; Duchin et al., 2017; Hu et al., 2017; Xiong & Gui, 2019), influencing factors (Du et al., 2019; Gunnoe, 2016; Peng et al., 2018; Perillo & Battiston, 2020; Wu & Bai, 2019; Zou, 2018), and economic consequences (Du et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2019; Xu, 2021) of corporate financialization. However, scholars also point out that because corporations exist in a social environment, managers' behavioral decisions are influenced not only by factors within the corporation itself, but also by peer corporations interlocked because of social networks. They refer to this rational, selective, non-blind herding phenomenon of referring to peer corporations to help their own behavioral decisions as the peer effect of corporate behavior (Almazan et al., 2010; Manski, 1993; Shue, 2013; Lu & Chang, 2018; Yi et al., 2019).

Social networks are formed based on the social relationships owned by modern corporations, which contain various types of social capital, such as information, knowledge, reputation, strategic resources, and decision-making influence. Interlocking director networks are the main form of corporate social networks, referring to the direct or indirect network relationships formed by individual directors

serving on the boards of different companies at the same time (Larcker et al., 2013), and directors who serve on two or more boards at the same time are called interlocking directors. In fact, interlocking director network relationships cover almost the entire Chinese capital market. In 2016, approximately 94.19% of the boards of directors of listed companies in the Shanghai and Shenzhen A-share markets had at least one interlocking director. In a "relationship-oriented society" like China, interlocking director networks, as an important information transmission path, play an important role in corporate governance. It has been found that corporations are influenced by interlocking director networks in terms of M&A behavior (Almazan et al., 2010), investment behavior (Fracassi, 2017) and executive compensation (Albuquerque et al., 2013), resulting in a peer effect. Thus, this study suggests its first question as, "What is the impact of interlocking director networks on the financialization of non-financial corporations?"

Risk-taking is the willingness of a company to take risks as a price in order to pursue high returns (John et al., 2008). Financial assets offer higher returns and greater risks than industrial investments, requiring companies that take financial investment decisions to increase their risk-taking level. Interlocking directors are usually involved in important decision-making activities in the dual role of supervisor and advisor, and the interlocking director networks have constituted a medium for low-cost information transfer between corporations (Macaulay et al., 2018), can they contribute to corporate financialization by increasing the level of risk-taking of the firm and, consequently, its financialization? This leads to the second question of this study, "Does risk-taking assume a mediating role in the effect of interlocking director networks on the corporate financialization?"

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

This study analyzes its impact on the corporate financialization based on both the network position of the corporation in the interlocking director networks and the strength of the ties.

Based on social network theory and resource dependence theory, director networks formed by interlocked directors facilitate the exchange and diffusion of information and resources among corporations. Woolcock(1998) pointed out that the access to social capital has a structural end, and the access to capital and the efficiency of its utilization depend on the structural location of interlocked directors. The higher the value of centrality as a core indicator of network structure location, the broader the scope of the corporation's directors' concurrent appointments and the more important their network location. Directors who are at the center of the director network can utilise their information advantage and access to more external information resources. Therefore, they are more likely to be influenced by the financialization behavior of peer corporations and make financialization investment decisions. Based on above analysis, this paper proposes Hypothesis 1.

H1: The director network centrality shows a positive relationship with corporate financialization, i.e., the greater the network centrality of a non-financial corporation, the greater the impact of the director network peer effect on corporate financialization behavior.

The "core" corporations in the director network have access to more information, technology, and social capital, which can reduce information asymmetry and uncertainty, thus enhancing managers' confidence and risk tolerance, and increasing corporate risk-taking level. A higher level of risk-taking implies that corporations have a stronger motivation and willingness to invest in high-return, high-risk investment projects. Financial asset investment projects are characterized by high risks, and corporations need to invest in financial assets based on their own risk-taking ability. If a corporation's risk-taking ability is higher, it means that its willingness and propensity to invest in high-risk and high-return projects is also higher, and the corporation is likely to allocate more financial assets, thus promoting the peer effect of corporate financialization.

H2: The network location of interlocked directors shows a positive relationship with corporate risk-taking, i.e., the higher the centrality of the interlocked director in director network, the stronger the level of risk-taking.

H3: Director network centrality facilitates corporate financialization by increasing the level of risk-taking, i.e., there is a mediating effect of corporate risk-taking between director network centrality and corporate financialization.

Granovetter(1973) defined the strength of ties based on four elements: time of acquaintance, frequency of interaction, degree of intimacy, and reciprocal exchange, classifying the strength of ties between individuals in a social network structure. In the network structure of directors, they can be divided into internal directors (executive directors) and external directors (independent directors) according to the nature of their positions, and both have large differences in the strength of the ties due to their different socio-economic characteristics. Most of the internal directors do not have clear boundaries with management and have relatively limited cognition and high information overlap due to the common working environment, which is consistent with the strong tie traits. External directors are mostly leaders of industry associations, professionals and university professors, who have little contact with each other and mainly rely on regular board meetings or private occasions for communication. Moreover, their diverse backgrounds provide companies with a wider range of heterogeneous information sources, and they can easily act as information transmission links across social boundaries, which is consistent with the weak tie traits. In this paper, we adopt Li Yang et al.'s (2019) criteria for defining the strength of directors' ties, where strong ties involve only ties established between internal directors and weak ties include ties established between external directors and between internal and external directors (at least one of whom is an external director).

Under strong ties, internal board members are exposed to a relative lack of external information and a basic convergence of knowledge and experience, which results in a repetitive cycle of limited information and increases the level of infor-

mation redundancy. This discourages internal directors from making strategic recommendations on investment behavior, thereby inhibiting corporate financialization. On the contrary, under weak ties, external directors can bring diversified and scarce information resources to the corporations, which promotes learning and imitation among them, thus facilitating corporate financialization.

H4: There is a differentiated relationship between the strength of director ties and corporate financialization, in which strong ties formed by internal directors inhibit corporate financialization and weak ties formed by external directors promote corporate financialization.

Based on the reputation mechanism, internal directors focus on maintaining and enhancing their own reputation and prestige, and are likely to be more risk-averse and use their influence to oppose investment projects with higher risks. This reduces the corporate risk-taking level, which in turn reduces their intention to invest in financial assets. On the contrary, based on resource dependence theory, external directors can help corporations obtain external resources at a lower cost and help alleviate the financing constraints of corporate risk-taking behavior. At the same time, the information advantage that external directors have can help decision makers better anticipate future uncertainties, thus enhancing their risk appetite and increasing their risk-taking incentives, which in turn promotes corporate financialization. Based on the above analysis, this study proposes hypotheses 5 and 6.

H5: The strong ties formed by internal directors inhibit corporate financialization by reducing the level of risk-taking, i.e., there is a mediating effect of corporate risk-taking between the strong ties formed by internal directors and corporate financialization.

H6: Weak ties formed by outside directors promote corporate financialization by increasing the level of risk-taking, i.e., corporate risk-taking mediates between weak ties formed by inside directors and corporate financialization.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

In the existing literature on interlocking director networks, risk-taking, and corporate financialization, many scholars have used quantitative methods to analyze their relationships with other constructs. This study will draw on their approach to analyze the correlations among interlocking director networks, risk-taking, and corporate financialization through quantitative research.

The empirical analysis of this study will be conducted in five steps. The first step, quantitative construction. Refer to the relevant literature to determine the measurement of each construct. In the second step, data collection. This study will use Chinese A-share non-financial listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen as the research sample and obtain the data required for the study from CSMAR database.

The third step, main effects test, examines the correlation between interlocking director networks and corporate financialization. The fourth step, the mediating effect test, examines the mechanism of the influence between interlocking director networks on corporate financialization, i.e., the mediating effect of risk-taking. The fifth step, robustness test.

FINDINGS

The expected findings of this study are as follows. First, there is a positive relationship between director network centrality and corporate financialization, in which risk-taking plays a mediating role. Second, there is a differentiated relationship between the strength of director ties and corporate financialization, in which strong ties formed by internal directors inhibit corporate financialization and weak ties formed by external directors promote corporate financialization, and risk-taking plays a mediating role.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

First, most of the existing literature defines peer corporations from the perspective of industry and geographic location; this study provides a new perspective for the study of the peer effect from the perspective of peer corporations formed by interlocking director networks.

Second, unlike the previous literature, this study focuses not only on the relationship between interlocking director networks and corporate financialization, but also on their intrinsic mechanisms and influence paths, which will help to understand the deeper reasons for the trend of financialization of non-financial corporations.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

This study has several potential implications. First, at the theoretical level, this study will help to enrich the theoretical application scope of the peer effect of corporate behavior. In recent years, based on behavioral economics theory, more and more scholars have paid attention to the influence of the peer effect on the behavioral decisions of companies, but there is a lack of systematic research on financialization. This study investigates the role of the peer effect on the trend of corporate financialization from the perspective of directors' network, which helps to understand the phenomenon of financialization in China's economy and provides scientific basis and practical reference for macro-prudential policy adjustment at the micro level.

Second, from a research perspective, this study will systematically match firm-level microdata with meso-level data of director network peer corporations based

on combining existing research and relevant theories. In this way, it will reflect the impact and the existence of group differences in their role as direct bearers of financialization behavior.

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